

STUDY OF MICROALGAE GROWTH IN A PHOTOBIOREACTOR

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Abstract. *In the article photobioreactors microalgae is chlorella chlorella vulgar vulgar learn grow grass the grass in the example of the water was conducted in the environment cultural water to grow feed , and feed fluid to increase the number of cells in their content of the environment by taking into account elements that should be saved and micro macro experiments conducted. Photobioreactor water the grass chlorella vulgar study of growth on we can say that research is based microwater the growth and development of the grassrollers to external factors which effect them in place the development of sish, which is a change in meaning. In particular, the effect of continuous light in the water the grass chlorella vulgarto growth and development, positive impact.*

Keywords: *photobioreactor, Chlorella vulgar, environment, feed, feed structure of the elements in the environment, bright, social, temperature, barbarian, directed were: value, biologically active substances, vitamins, microelement.*

In the years of independence, significant attention has been given to improving the living conditions and social protection of the population by our President and government. In particular, efforts have focused on ensuring the biological value and safety of both eco-friendly and safe food products, as well as medicinal drugs. For instance, the decree No. PF-5853 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 23, 2019, "On the approval of the strategy for the development of agriculture in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030," and the decree No. PF-5995 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 18, 2020, "On additional measures to ensure the compliance of quality and safety indicators of agricultural products with international standards," emphasize not only the provision of the population with organically grown products but also the supply of naturally occurring biologically active substances.

Moreover, the President's decision No. PQ-4899 dated November 25, 2020, "On comprehensive measures to develop biotechnology and improve the system for ensuring the country's biological security," clearly defines the work to be carried out in this direction.

Due to the development of biotechnology, interest in biologically active substances, particularly those naturally occurring and essential for the human body, such as vitamins, microelements, and other high-value biological substances, has significantly increased in recent years. It is well-known that vitamins play an essential role in the body's functioning, and their sources in nature are various fruits, vegetables, microorganisms, and microalgae.

Chlorella, a type of green algae, represents microscopic aquatic plants. Adding chlorella to the feed of agricultural animals can increase their weight by up to 40% and improve livestock

productivity to 99%. This is achieved due to the unique biological nature of chlorella as a natural product [1,2,4].

The study of microalgae growth in a photobioreactor was conducted using *Chlorella vulgaris*. The nutrient medium for growing *Chlorella vulgaris* and promoting cell reproduction should contain macro and microelements. The elements present in the liquid nutrient medium of the photobioreactor are listed in Table 1 [2,3].

Macro and microelements necessary for the normal life of *Chlorella vulgaris* aquatic plant cells:

Element	The value of the element
K	Cells affect osmotic pressure and water-salt balance
Mg	Chlorophyll is a compound Activates Krebs cycle enzymes Carbohydrates and lipids are also involved in aerobic decomposition
S	Contains cysteine and methionine Energetic metabolism is involved in reactions
P	cell membranes include phospholipids participates in protein synthesis Provides energy renewal (ATP)
Mn	Necessary for normal photosynthesis It is part of the center of the photosystem It is important to preserve the composition of chloroplast Activates 35 enzymes It also activates the Krebs cycle catalyzing enzymes
Zn	Participates in breathing Participates in protein metabolism
B	Participates in the metabolism of nucleic acids It causes competitive inhibition of some enzymes

Each macro and microelement in the nutrient solution has its specific role and function in the medium. A deficiency or absence of any element in the nutrient medium prevents *Chlorella vulgaris* from fully expressing its characteristics. In other words, the growth phase of *Chlorella vulgaris* may not meet the required standards, and the balance of bioactive substances produced by the algae may be disrupted [5,6].

Our experiments were conducted in a photobioreactor with a capacity of 5 liters. *Chlorella vulgaris* was grown and developed in a nutrient medium prepared by us under standard conditions in the photobioreactor for 10 days. The results obtained are shown in Table 2.

Table 2

Cultivation period of algae	The number of cells in 100 ml of culture fluid
Day 1	2.5 x 10 ⁷
Day 3	3 x 10 ⁷
Day 5	3.25 x 10 ⁷
Day 7	4 x 10 ⁷
Day 10	5 x 10 ⁷

As seen from the table, *Chlorella vulgaris* algae exhibited steady growth in the photobioreactor.

In the second phase of our experiments, during the growth period of *Chlorella vulgaris* in the photobioreactor under standard conditions, oxygen was supplied to the environment, and the growth and development of the algae were observed for an additional 10 days. The results obtained are shown in Table 3. From the table, it is clear that the introduction of air into the photobioreactor's environment can have a slight impact on the growth and development of *Chlorella vulgaris*. Growth in the photobioreactor was observed to be somewhat higher compared to the growth under normal conditions.

Table 3

Cultivation period of algae	The number of cells in 100 ml of culture fluid
Day 1	2.5 x 10 ⁷
Day 3	3 x 10 ⁷
Day 5	3.5 x 10 ⁷
Day 7	4.1 x 10 ⁷
Day 10	5.2 x 10 ⁷

In the next phase of our experiments, *Chlorella vulgaris* was grown in the photobioreactor under standard conditions, but this time with a continuous light source, providing light day and night. The growth and development of *Chlorella vulgaris* under these conditions were observed for an additional 10 days. The results are shown in Table 4. From the table, it is evident that providing continuous light in the photobioreactor environment can significantly affect the growth and development of *Chlorella vulgaris*.

Table 4

Cultivation period of algae	The number of cells in 100 ml of culture fluid
Day 1	2.5 x 10 ⁷
Day 3	3.5 x 10 ⁷
Day 5	4 x 10 ⁷
Day 7	4.9 x 10 ⁷
Day 10	7.5 x 10 ⁷

In the fourth phase of our experiments, *Chlorella vulgaris* was grown under conditions where the photobioreactor was continuously supplied with both light and air. The growth and development of *Chlorella vulgaris* were observed for an additional 10 days under these conditions. The results are shown in Table 5. From the table, it is clear that the growth and development of *Chlorella vulgaris* under continuous light and air conditions in the photobioreactor are almost the same as the results obtained under continuous light alone, with only a slight difference.

Table 5

Cultivation period of algae	The number of cells in 100 ml of culture fluid
Day 1	2.5 x 10 ⁷
Day 3	3.6x 10 ⁷
Day 5	4 x 10 ⁷
Day 7	5 x 10 ⁷
Day 10	7.6 x 10 ⁷

Based on the research we conducted on the growth and development of *Chlorella vulgaris* in the photobioreactor, we can conclude that when external factors influence the growth and development of microalgae, certain changes occur in their development. Specifically, continuous exposure to light positively affects the growth and development of *Chlorella vulgaris*.

CONCLUSION:

In cultivating *Chlorella vulgaris* algae cells in a nutrient medium, the composition of the nutrient medium, the design of the photobioreactor, and the intensity of light are of particular importance.

Scientific research analysis shows that *Chlorella vulgaris* algae cells contain biologically active substances that are important for enriching food products. Therefore, studying the growth and development of *Chlorella vulgaris* algae is a pressing issue.

In cultivating *Chlorella vulgaris* in a nutrient medium, different external influences (such as creating stress conditions) were observed to affect their growth and development to varying degrees.

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